

NEW TECHNOLOGIES FOR INCREASING OIL AND GAS PRODUCTIVITY

Za'ripbaev Tursinbay Sarsenbay uli,

*Faculty of Geography and Natural Resources Oil and Gas Supply
2nd year student*

Abstract: *The problem of innovation is a key one for most of the industrialized countries of the world. Scientific and technical products resulting from intellectual activity need to create a system of protection of industrial property rights, which is a mandatory attribute of developed countries. The transition of the economy to a new qualitative state increases the importance of innovation and the development of high-tech industries, which, ultimately, are the most important factor in overcoming the economic crisis and providing conditions for economic growth.*

Key words: *innovation; oil and gas companies; scientific and technical products; potential; oil and gas revenues; oil production; intensification; oil production*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7713694>

The role of technological innovations in the exploration and production of oil and gas during the energy transition is considered. The main trends in the development of oil and gas innovations at the present stage, the amount of funding and the main participants are determined. The types of innovations are described and the role of "destructive" innovations is shown. The potential for reducing specific operating costs due to new technologies is indicated. Examples of the effective use of digital technologies in leading in a world wide oil and gas companies are given.

Price pressure and a change in demand in the oil and gas sector make the task of realizing potential cost, embedded in modern capabilities of connecting to networks, more important than ever for companies of the reconnaissance and production sector.

According to McKinsey & Company, the use of advanced tools providing connecting various objects to optimize the performance of drilling and mining, as well as to improve maintenance and work in the field, by 2030, it can add up to 250 billion dollars to the cost created in the Apstim sector. Of this amount, from 160 to 180 billion dollars can be obtained in the conditions of existing infrastructure, while the remaining \$ 70 billion can be implemented when using low-orbit satellites (NOSO) and technologies of the next Generations 5G.

Such a powerful technological rise cannot happen very quickly. The oil and gas industry has experienced the third price collapse over the past 12 years. After the first two shocks, it recovered and the business returned to the usual direction - with the same as before, a lack of attention to efficiency and costs. The current fall is different, since the sector is experiencing a sharp. A change in the situation with a proposal in combination with an unprecedented decrease in demand and a global humanitarian crisis.

Today, when prices reach 30 years of minimums and the pressure from society is growing, the leaders of oil and gas companies feel that the changes are inevitable. A crisis, The Covid-19 caused, significantly accelerated the previously formed trends that lead the industry to one of the largest transformations in its entire history.

In the long run there is another important factor that determines the need for significant operational improvements - the requirement to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. Investors devote everything more attention of environmental issues, energy prices from renewable sources fall, and more and more countries are taxed by enterprises with CO2 emissions. Production operations of industrial enterprises create 9% of all emissions produced by humans greenhouse gases of categories 1 and 2, and for the share of the produced.

The fuel industry accounts for a third of category 3 emissions. Although it is not known how deep and long the current crisis will be, our studies show that without fundamental changes it is unlikely that you can return to good industry indicators that were characteristic of the industry in the past. The most stable companies will be companies that boldly change their portfolio of projects and revise operating models, correctly using new technologies.

To date, industry connectivity levels vary considerably between players and destinations. For example, new deep-water offshore platforms have a high level of network connectivity – it is carried out using fiber optic and microwave lines. At the same time, onshore production facilities in more mature fields in regions such as the Middle East and Mexico, where three-quarters of the world's oil is produced, are still not well connected.

Objects that account for about 60% of this onshore production volume are connected using a microwave signal, and the rest - using VSAT. In Kazakhstan, the connection of oil and gas facilities to the network also varies greatly. At some of our fields, the connection is provided using fiber-optic communication lines and microwave, at others - via satellite networks, there are also fields that do not have a network connection at all, and any work in the field is carried out using mobile communication stations. Unfortunately, for the oil and gas fields of Kazakhstan, where the connection is provided by VSAT stations, the economic the benefits of digital operations and analytical work are not fully available. Opportunities to create value with modern connectivity technologies Technology creates the potential to increase productivity throughout the oil and gas industry's value chain through optimization and automation. Optimization involves the use of all the various data with a certain frequency for making more informed decisions. Automation involves the use of automatic or semi-automatic devices instead of humans to carry out work in high-risk conditions. To demonstrate the variety of possibilities offered by modern connectivity technologies, we'll look at five examples: drilling time reduction, production increase, smart maintenance, improved field operation, and improved logistics.

Speaking of optimization drilling, our experience with upstream companies shows that advanced analysis methods can help operators reduce drilling time downtime twice. Drilling speed can increase by 25% or more, which will result in lower costs per well, as well as reduce pollution associated with drilling and related operations, by

almost 10%. Modern connection technologies also allow for remote or semi-automatic drilling, which significantly reduces the number of people who need to be present on the rig itself. Automation will also reduce dependence on human factor during tripping operations, which will lead to increased efficiency. According to our estimates, the useful work during drilling will increase up to 94% from today's 90%.

Significant investment in new capabilities and technologies will be required, although not as massive as as always allocated for capital projects. It will also require significant shifts in the corporate culture of industry players, in data and workforce practices, in business models and ecosystems, as well as potential changes in regulation. The task ahead is not easy. However, the hundreds of billions of dollars of potential value that could be created as a result make such investments and changes worthwhile, especially as we begin to return to post-crisis living conditions.

References

1. Dunaev V.F. Economics of oil and gas industry enterprises: textbook. Moscow: izdatel'stvo «Nef't' i gaz» RGU nefti i gaza im. Gubkina, 2006, 352 p. Available at: <https://economuch.com/otrasli-ekonomika/ekonomikapredpriyatij-neftyanoy-gazovoy.html>. (In Russ.)
2. Linnik V., Linnik Yu. Priority directions of innovative development in oil and gas complex at the Siberian Federal District. Upravlenie, 2019, no. 3, pp. 40–49. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26425/2309-3633-2019-1-40-49>. (In Russ.)
3. Ismailov Kh.F., Brazhnikov M.A. Intensification of production based on the introduction of progressive technologies in PJSC «NK Rosneft». Molodoi uchenyi, 2020, no. 43 (333), pp. 23–25. Available at: <https://moluch.ru/archive/333/74337/>; <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44138968>. (In Russ.)
4. Manukyan M.M. Current state of oil and gas industry in Russia and its development trends. Vestnik Samarskogo universiteta. Ekonomika i upravlenie = Vestnik of Samara University. Economics and Management, 2020, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 34–43. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.18287/2542-0461-2020-11-1-34-42>. (In Russ.)
5. Klyucharev G.A., Popov M.S., Savinkov V.I. Innovative enterprises in higher education institutions: issues of integration with the real sector of economy. 2nd edition, revised and enlarged. Moscow: Izdatel'stvo Iurait, 2020,